

OPTIMIZING ANDROID APPLICATION PERFORMANCE: MODERN METHODS AND PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the impact of mobile application (MA) performance optimization on the digital marketplace. It discusses the key performance metrics of Android MA for evaluating application quality. Various aspects of optimization are considered, including the use of native Android NDK and JNI libraries and improved code structure. The use of profiling tools such as Android Profiler and Systrace is explored, as well as the use of advanced approaches such as asynchronous programming.

Keywords: performance optimization, Android, mobile applications (MA), memory management, profiling, Key Performance Indicators (KPI), native libraries.

Introduction

In today's world, the use of smartphones for leisure and work has become one of the most essential parts of people's lives. As the popularity of such devices grows, so does the demand for mobile applications (MA) that provide high quality and performance. However, in the pursuit of speeding up the development process, specialists may neglect fundamental programming principles, leading to numerous issues related to optimization. The high competition in the MA market requires not only functionality but also fast, smooth performance, minimized energy consumption, and efficient use of device resources.

Optimizing MA encompasses various aspects, including efficient memory management, reducing CPU load, optimizing network requests, and improving interface rendering. Modern methods may include the use

of profiling tools, as well as the implementation of advanced architectural approaches and technologies. Adopting such practices can enhance the user experience (UX) and improve the performance of Android-based MA. The aim of this article is to explore modern methods and practices aimed at improving the performance of Android applications.

Main part. Analysis of the impact of Android application performance on the digital product market

The performance quality of MA plays a crucial role in their ranking and market position. In a highly competitive environment where users have a wide range of alternatives, the quality of digital products directly influences the demand and popularity of MA [1]. The number of mobile application downloads has been steadily increasing each year, with this figure surpassing 250 billion downloads in 2023 (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Number of MA downloads worldwide from 2016 to 2023, in billions [2]

When optimizing MA on the Android operating system, developers have a greater chance of success by improving their rankings in digital store search results. This popularity is driven by the flexibility of Android, which allows developers and device manufacturers to customize and modify the system according to their needs.

As the platform and its MA scale, the number of system load-related issues may increase [3]. According to estimates from the cloud-based mobile attribution and analytics platform Appsflyer, the average daily

user retention rate on Android decreased by approximately 12% in 2023 compared to the previous year [4]. This indicates that retaining users has become a more challenging task amid growing competition and rising user expectations.

In this context, key performance indicators (KPI) play a crucial role in assessing the performance and quality of Android-based MA. Analyzing KPI helps developers identify how well they are meeting customer needs and find ways to improve application performance (table 1).

Table 1.

Key performance indicators of MA [5]	
KPI	Description
App startup time	Measures the amount of time it takes for the mobile application to fully load and display the first screen.
UI Responsiveness	Determines the speed of the UI's response to user actions, such as tapping and scrolling. It is crucial for creating a smooth UX.
Memory usage	Monitors the amount of RAM usage. High consumption can lead to memory leaks and crashes.
Scroll performance	Measures the frame rate and smoothness of scrolling.
Network performance	Indicates the execution time of network requests and the volume of data transmitted.
Battery usage	Determines the impact of the application's operation on battery life. It is important to minimize the use of resource-intensive processes.
Crash rate	Evaluates the number of crashes and errors per thousand sessions. A low error rate is critical for the stability of the application.

These KPI enable developers not only to analyze the performance of their applications but also to identify which aspects require optimization to enhance UX and reduce churn. Continuous monitoring and improvement of these metrics help professionals create more efficient and popular applications.

Analysis of effective methods and practices for enhancing the performance of android-based MA

In the context of growing competition and high user expectations for MA, performance optimization has become one of the most critical tasks in development. Various modern approaches are employed to achieve stability, responsiveness, and minimize resource consumption in Android applications.

The foundation for improving MA performance lies in **code optimization and improving its structure**. Refactoring with a focus on modularity and reusability helps reduce complexity and improve application maintainability. Methods such as Lazy Loading and deferred initialization allow for loading only the necessary resources at the right time. Deferred loading of images and data reduces memory and CPU load, ultimately increasing the application's response speed. The use of efficient algorithms and loops for data processing, avoiding redundant computations, and reducing the number of repetitive operations can significantly reduce execution time and resource consumption.

Profiling is one of the most crucial stages in the process of optimizing Android applications. This analysis method helps identify performance bottlenecks, locate areas of excessive resource usage, and make informed optimization decisions [6]. Profiling covers aspects such as CPU and memory usage, network operations, and interface rendering. Several modern technologies exist for this method, allowing for effective participation in the development and optimization of Android-based applications.

One such tool is the built-in **Android Profiler** in Android studio, which provides detailed real-time data on the application's performance. It includes the Memory Profiler, which allows for tracking memory usage, identifying objects that occupy a lot of space, and detecting memory leaks. This module helps prevent «OutOfMemory» errors and improves application stability.

Another component, the CPU Profiler, shows which methods and threads take the most execution time. It helps identify costly operations and optimize them, reducing CPU load and increasing interface responsiveness. The Network Profiler module displays network operation execution times, data transfer volumes, and request types. This tool can be relevant for optimizing server interactions and reducing latency when working with data. It can also be used for proper memory management.

Another effective technology is **Systrace**, which is designed to analyze device performance at the system level. It collects trace logs that help assess the execution time of various processes, such as rendering, event processing, and hardware interactions [7]. This tool allows diagnosing interface delays caused by rendering issues or long input/output operations. The technology helps understand which processes consume the most resources and how they interact with the application.

Using native libraries allows developers to leverage device capabilities at a low level, ensuring maximum performance for critical operations. The Java Native Interface (JNI) tool enables the integration of code written in C or C++ into Android applications. This method is widely used for computationally intensive tasks, such as graphics processing or mathematical computations. The use of native code via JNI helps increase execution speed and reduce system load.

Another popular technology is **Android NDK** (Native Development Kit), which provides access to native libraries and tools [8]. This allows developers to optimize the handling of multimedia files, graphics, and other resources that require high performance. Through JNI, developers can directly interact with the device's hardware, such as the graphics processor, allowing for more efficient use of device resources.

Asynchronous programming (AP) is an essential component of high-performance Android applications. In multitasking operating systems like Android, blocking operations can negatively impact the user experience, causing interface delays and reducing overall application performance. The use of AP allows for executing long tasks in the background, freeing up the main UI thread for handling user interactions. The primary approach in this technology is the use of coroutines. They allow for easy switching between threads without adding unnecessary complexity to the

code. Integrated into Kotlin, coroutines have become the standard solution for AP in Android, helping to prevent interface freezes during heavy operations.

As the number of users grows, well-optimized MAs can handle high loads and ensure stable performance. This is a crucial factor for successful scaling, improving UX, and ensuring data security, especially in financial applications [9].

Future directions and challenges in Android application performance optimization

As the landscape of MA continues to evolve, the optimization of Android app performance will face new challenges and opportunities. The increasing complexity of applications, driven by advanced features like artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and real-time data processing, will demand even more sophisticated optimization techniques. Developers will need to stay abreast of emerging technologies, such as machine learning for automated optimization, enhanced profiling tools, and more efficient ways to manage power consumption and resource allocation.

The growing diversity of Android devices, each with different hardware configurations and performance capabilities, will require more adaptive and scalable optimization strategies. Ensuring that applications perform consistently across various devices will be crucial for maintaining user satisfaction and market competitiveness.

In addition to technical challenges, developers will also need to address issues related to transparency and user trust. As optimization techniques become more complex, maintaining the balance between performance and user privacy will be vital. The development community will need to ensure that optimization practices do not compromise data security or lead to unintended consequences in user experience.

While current methods and practices provide a solid foundation for optimizing Android applications, ongoing innovation and adaptability will be essential for addressing future challenges. By continuing to refine and expand upon these techniques, developers can create MA that not only meet but exceed the growing expectations of users in an increasingly competitive digital environment.

Conclusions

The optimization of Android application performance is becoming increasingly important in the face of high competition and growing user demands. Efficient resource management and minimization of delays

are among the key factors determining the success of MA. A comprehensive approach to performance optimization involves the application of modern methods and practices. These include the use of profiling tools, the implementation of AP with coroutines, and code optimization. Such strategies enable the creation of MA that meet user expectations, ensuring high stability, speed, and smooth operation.

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